

Substitution of silica by active alumina in triaxial porcelain

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Triaxial composition has been constituted taking precipitated silica as a component in place of quartz and this was substituted gradually by active alumina. Alumina minimized the glass content and also changed the nature of the residual glass, which resulted a significant change in the properties, and the microstructure of the fired bodies. Under the condition, the maturing temperature has been lowered compared to traditional porcelain.

Fine ceramics articles have played an important role in the modern day technology. Rigidity, resistance to abrasion and chemical attack, bad conductor of heat made it useful in our daily life. With addition of alumina strength increases in porcelain¹ and with zinc oxide and lithium minerals lowering of firing temperature takes place².

Various substitutions have been tried in this triaxial system³. The glassy phase in the triaxial system limits the application as a high performance material. Present investigation was undertaken to incorporate alumina as a substitute of silica in the composition.

The main objective of the present investigation was to compose a triaxial body with improved thermo-mechanical properties.

Experimental

For compiling the composition, Rajmahal china clay and feldspar of Bihar deposit were selected along with technical alumina and precipitated silica. The fabricated shapes after proper drying were fired in an electrically heated furnace for a fixed soaking period of two hours. XRD analysis of the fired samples were carried out using a Philips Per (1970) X-ray diffractometer. Microstructure was analysed in a scanning electron microscope named Hitachi-S-530.

Results and discussion

The first manifestation of this type of solid state reaction in a poly-component system is the shrinkage of the compacted mass. This is very much related to the reaction amongst the component oxides. The linear shrinkage was found to be positive function of temperature up to 1350°C (Fig. 1). From 1250°C to 1350°C the relative change was not much significant. At 1400°C except for Batch-I shrink-

Fig. 1a. Relationship between % linear shrinkage vs firing temperature.

Fig. 1b. Relationship between % linear shrinkage vs % Al₂O₃.

age decreased which might be due to generation of low density phases with Al₂O₃. It is to be noted here that reactivity enhanced due to incorporation of precipitated silica above 1350°C.

The bulk density of the fired samples is related to actual densification of the body which followed a direct relationship with temperature. Maximum densification was found to be about 95%. With the gradual addition of Al₂O₃ bulk

density decreased although the magnitude of change was not of high order.

The expulsion of water from the body generates pores in the standard triaxial body. The general tendency of a triaxial body on firing is the reduction of porosity through the formation of liquid and subsequent interlocking of the crystal. Porosity reduction with temperature exhibited inflection at 1300°C. From 1350°C to 1400°C the change in porosity was not so much significant. The flat region with Batch-I and Batch-II might be related to the fluxing action of feldspar, which possessed high viscosity and long fusion range. Even high Al₂O₃ containing bodies exhibited sufficient reduction of porosity at 1350°C. This might be due to the higher activity of the body mixture.

Aluminous porcelain is a suitable material for electrical insulation. The volume resistivity fired at 1350°C and 1400°C are given in Table 1. The volume resistivity decreased with increase in temperature, which might be related to the formation of more glassy phase. Regarding the compositional effect, resistivity decreased with increase in alumina content. This was due to the more ionic nature of Al₂O₃ than SiO₂. From the XRD pattern the major crystalline phase was found to be mullite, the most important stable phase in aluminosilicate system along with minor amount of corundum, whose intensity increased with increase in Al₂O₃ content.

Table 1. Volume resistivity of the reaction-sintered samples fired at different temperatures (Percentage of clay 50, feldspar 25 in all batches)

Batch no.	Percentage of ppt.		Volume resistivity (MW) of the samples fired at	
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	1350°C	1400°C
I	25	0	92.01	98.00
II	15	10	86.04	83.26
III	10	15	80.08	71.94
IV	5	20	71.01	59.88

Finally the microstructural study was performed using scanning electron microscope with the selective samples fired at 1350°C. Micrographs of Batch-I and Batch-IV (Figs. 2(a) and (b)) indicated that with increase of Al₂O₃ content

Fig. 2a. SEM result of Batch no. I fired at 1350°C (at 6000X).

Fig. 2b. SEM result of Batch no. IV fired at 1350°C (at 6000X).

grain growth was accelerated which might be due to change in mullite composition. Moreover grain boundary became sharper and the morphology of mullite exhibited a change from elongated to equiaxed.

Conclusion :

The incorporation of Al₂O₃ as a substitute for SiO₂ changed the important properties of triaxial porcelain.

Precipitated SiO₂ as a substitute for quartz increased the reaction rate and as such the maturing temperature was found to be within 1300°C to 1350°C. The evolved microstructure with higher alumina content changed the grain shape and their distribution in the matrix.

References

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